

Popular Article

Native Herbs: Remedies for Reproductive Health

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Introduction

Herbs are plants that are used for medicine, cooking, food, flavor, etc. Herbs have additive and synergistic effects. Secondary metabolites of herbs increase therapeutic feasibility. The World Health Organization estimates that 80% of the world's population is dependent on traditional medicine, with more than 7500 plant species (herbs, etc.) are being used.

Benefits of Herbs: -

1. Herbal medicines are very cheap.
2. They have a negligible adverse effect on health.
3. The body's natural detoxification process is effectively enhanced by the herbs.
4. Herbs help in regulating the immune system and mental health.
5. Herbs are effective in curing various diseases.

➤ Some of the important herbs used for improving female reproductive functions: -

Aloe vera, Bael, Ashoka, Peepal, Fennel, Ultakambal, Shatavari, Black cumin, Curry leaves, Sowa, Dong quai, Sundhi, Neem, Chitraka, Gokshura, Castor.

1. Aloe Vera

Scientific name - Aloe barbadensis (Aloe barbadensis)

Active ingredients – Two glycosides- Aloin, Barbaloin are obtained from it.

- Uses – (i) Treatment of various uterine disorders.
(ii) Aloe vera induces the onset of puberty.
(iii) Steroidogenesis induces the initiation of folliculogenesis

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2. Bael

Scientific name - *Aegle marmelos*

Active ingredients – Its husks contain two alkaloids – aeglenine and aegline.

Uses – Its estrogenic effect leads to the early onset of puberty, folliculogenesis and steroidogenesis.

Bael

3. Ashok

Scientific name – *Saraca asoca*

Active ingredients – Deoxyprocyanidin B, catechins, leucopelargonidin, and leucocyanidin are found in its bark.

Uses – (i) Stimulant action on uterus and ovaries.

(ii) Puberty at a young age through estrogenic effects.

Ashok

4. Peepal

Scientific name - *Ficus religiosa*

Active ingredients – (i) Its leaves contain calcium, iron, copper, manganese, zinc, tannic acid, amino acid, sterol substances

(ii) Vitamin K is found in its bark.

Uses – Its estrogenic effect leads to the early onset of puberty, folliculogenesis, and steroidogenesis.

Peepal

5. Fennel (Saunf)

Scientific name – *Foeniculum vulgare*

Active Ingredients – Anethole and its polymers such as dianethol and photoanethol are obtained from it.

Uses – (i) Its estrogenic effect induces the oestrus cycle.

(ii) Increase in libido.

Fennel

6. Devil's horn

Scientific name - *Abroma augusta*

Common name- Ulatkambal

Active Part – Its roots and leaves have estrogen activity.

Uses – Stimulating action of estrogenic effect on uterus and ovaries.

7. Black cumin / Kalonji (Black cumin)

Scientific name- *Nigella sativa*

Active part – Volatile oil is made from its seeds.

Uses – This volatile oil relaxes the muscles of the uterus and acts against oxytocin-induced uterine contractions.

8. Curry leaf plant

Scientific name- *Murraya koenigii*

The active part – in its leaves – Ca, P, Fe, carotene, vitamins A and C, and amino acids are obtained.

Uses – (i) Induces the female animal who has trouble in coming to the estrus cycle in them.

(ii) Induction of estrus in anestrous condition

9. Shatavari

Scientific name – *Asparagus racemosus*

Active Ingredients – Steroidal glycosides and aglycones, Shatavarin

are obtained from it. Shatavariin is rich in Ca, Mg, Cu, Fe, Mn, Fe, Ti, Z mineral elements.

Uses – (i) Early onset of puberty.

(ii) It is used in the treatment of the problem of reproduction of animals.

10. Neem

Scientific name – *Azadirachta indica*

Active Ingredients – Nimbin, isoprenoids, and norisoprenoids are

obtained from their seeds, bark, or leaves.

Uses – (i) The aqueous extract of neem is used to strengthen the immune system (Immunostimulant).

(ii) Neem oil is used in the prevention of inflammation in the uterus.

11. Sowa / Dill Seeds

Scientific name – *Anethum sowa*

Active Ingredients – N-butanol and petroleum ether are obtained from it.

Uses – (i) It is used for expulsion of fetal membranes after birth.

(ii) Giving in combination with calamus, crystal sugar, neem leaves, and onion bulb is used to treat fibroid uterus.

12. Castor bean/ Arandi

Scientific name - *Ricinus communis*

Active Ingredients – Phytosterol from its leaves and Ricinoleic acid from seeds.

Uses – (i) Phytosterols – Used for the expulsion of the placenta.

(ii) Ricinoleic acid - acts to increase the contraction of the uterus.

13. Chitraka/ White leadwort

Scientific name – *Plumbago zeylanica*

Active Ingredients – Plumbagin is obtained from its roots and leaves.

Uses – It stimulate the uterus, reduce inflammation, antioxidants and

strengthen the immune system (Uterotonic, ecbolic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunopotentiating action).

Sowa

Castor bean

Chitraka

Dong quai

14. Dong quai

Scientific name – *Angelina sinensis*

Active part-whole plant

Uses – Its aqueous extract is used to cause contraction of the uterus.

➤ Herbs to improve male fertility:-

1. **Gokshura (*Tribulus terrestris*)**- Stimulates spermatogenesis, improves semen production, is used to improve libido and fertility.

2. ***Panax ginseng*** – Contains ginsenoside which is used for penis stimulation and for improving fertility in male animals.

3. **Ashwagandha (*Astragalus membranaceus*)** – It is used to improve sperm motility and increase the number of live spermatozoa and motility of sperms.

Conclusion

Medicines made from herbs do not have any adverse effect on the body. These medicines are easily available and cheap. 70% of milch cattle are owned by small, marginal farmers and landless laborers. Hence it is the need of the hour that suitable, effective, and affordable alternative medicine should be used to fulfill this need. Many herbs/plants are used for the treatment of various reproductive disorders and show good results; however, scientific validation of these herbs is needed now.

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Herbal drugs			
Exapar	Aloe barbadensis, Citrullus colocynthis, pippali (Scindapus officinalis), Rubia cordifolia (Mangistha). Leptadenia reticulata (jivanti).	Expar - earlier expulsion of fetal membrane (4-3 hrs) earlier disappearance of lochia (2-9 days) and earlier onset of post partum estrous	
Uterotone	Saraca asoca, Aloe barbadensis, Aegle marmelos, Solanum xanthocarpum, Na tetraborate, ferrus sulphate and copper sulphate.	Clinical trial with uterotone have shown 63% cases placenta came out within 6-18 hrs	
Utrifit	Caespinia bonducela, Pegalum hormonela (antimicrobial and antiseptic action), Plumbago zeylanica (immunopotentiating effect)	Retained placenta - 82% success rate in early cases and in delayed cases i.e after 48 hrs, S R in 60%.	
Involon	Adhatoda vasica. Gloriosa superba. Plumbagin of Plumoago zeylanica. Hermene, Hermaline present in Harmal (Peganum harmala).	Antiinflammatory Antioxidant Ecobalic Uterotonic Effect Antimicrobial, Antiseptic	
Prajana	Mrigashi dharpattan (Pippali – pipur longum), Black piper.	Prajana estrus induction similar to that of synthetic estrogens	
Aloes compound	Aloes (Aloes indica) Hirabol (Balsamodendron Myrrh) Hurmala (Peganum Harmala) Kasis Bhasma	Estrous -62.5% buffaloes within 7 days . C R upto 77%	

